

Introducing Ethics by Design in Engineering Education: Designing COVID-19 Tracing Apps

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ABSTRACT

Including ethical concepts and considerations in engineering education has attracted significant interest in recent years, mainly due to the impact of some AI applications in different areas of our life. The use of case studies in teaching ethics is a well-known and useful approach. The debate related with a given case study helps students think about the implications, motivations and foreseeable impact of the technologies. This fact is in contrast with the common easy-thinking that technologies are neutral and that an engineer should not bother about ethics and does not have any responsibility at all. While many basic technologies may be considered neutral, more developed and complex systems are not so neutral; they have a motivation and some foreseeable impact and consequences. Thence, the main message is that engineers have a responsibility when developing these systems.

This paper presents a case study used in a course for Ph.D. students in a Technical University to introduce the concept of ethics by design and to stress the idea of responsible conduct in engineering. The case under study is the design and development of tracing applications for fighting against the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020. The analysis of the case requires to understand the basic technologies proposed, the different alternatives considered at that time, the basic facts related with the contagion chain and the main factors to be addressed, the consideration of the balance between public health rights and individual privacy rights, and the social aspects related with the acceptability by citizens.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introducing ethics for engineers

The first challenge addressed is how to introduce a topic such as ethics in a Technical University where there are no other degrees than strictly engineering ones (including electrical, mechanical, civil engineering, computer science and architecture). There are no major and minor degrees. Students have never taken a course on philosophy, history or anthropology, to mention some subjects, at the University. This fact limits the concepts and terms that may be used in the class.

For the experience presented in this paper an optional course offered to Ph.D. students is selected. The main target are students in any of the Doctoral Programs of the University, so that a broad view of many areas in engineering are covered. Also, being Ph.D. students from different countries, their background knowledge and cultural environments are diverse. This approach helps to cope somehow with the intrinsic limitation of the lack of humanistic formation provided by the Technical University and provides a much richer discussion with different points of view than with a more homogeneous group.

The method presented and the same case study, or a similar one, may be used for undergraduate students.

1.2 The use of case studies

Using case studies for teaching ethics is a common practice and there is a general agreement that they are very useful. Discussing cases helps students to recognize ethical issues, to foster their analytical skills in ethics, to stimulate students' ethical imagination, to promote a sense of responsibility and to help students to deal with disagreement about ethical issues [1].

The first issue to be addressed, at least based on my experience, is the general perception that engineers deal with technology only and their job is neutral from the point of view of ethics. Despite the students enrolled in this optional course may have some curiosity about ethical implications, the underlying perception is that technology is neutral and this easy-thinking approach is dominant among engineering students.

The analysis of cases allows students to recognize the presence of ethical problems where initially we saw only technical issues, help them to develop their reasoning and assessment skills about the consequences and impact, help them to stimulate their moral imagination looking for possible alternatives, help them to acknowledge the limitations of the codes of ethics and regulations, and help them to understand that sometimes there is no best solution [2].

The use of case studies is of utmost relevance in teaching ethics because, as commonly agreed, "ethics is not so much taught as caught".

The case study selected is the development of tracing systems for Covid-19 that was the hot topic during spring 2020. This case presents a variety of approaches and

requires understanding the technical background; this catches the attention of engineering students.

The development of tracing applications for Covid-19 was undertaken immediately once the pandemic was declared worldwide. The design of these systems took many different paths, perhaps as many as countries, because politicians and healthcare authorities were overwhelmed by the impact on the pandemic and the need to have a tool to help cutting its spread was urgent.

2 METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the discussion of this case is to mimic to some extent the situation of the development of the tracing systems since their early conception and design choices. This implies to work with the information available about the pandemic and the behaviour of the virus, information that was evolving, and the considerations about the feasibility of real deployments of the new systems.

In order to highlight the importance of the interdisciplinarity of the problem the debate is introduced step by step. First of all, a deep understanding of the contagion chain and the conditions to stop its spread is required. Next, a sound assessment of the technology available and of the different alternatives is a key aspect that must be analysed. Then, the view of the healthcare staff involved, the capacities and participation required from the citizens (social impact), the existing regulations about how the information is managed and who has access to the data (which may depend on each country), and the analysis of privacy aspects are introduced in the discussion. The objective of the debate is to follow the whole design process of the system, impersonating the roles involved and reassessing past views when required.

The discussion is organized in two sessions in consecutive weeks. For the first session the students should read a short paper with the basic concepts about the spread of the infection and the requirements to cut the spread chain together with the technological approaches available. Before the discussion they are asked to fill a questionnaire to get an idea of the comprehension of both the health-related aspects and the technological ones.

The first session is dedicated to reach a common agreement about what is needed from a tracing system and what alternatives may be available from the technical point of view. Nowadays, how the infection spreads is mainly understood but some of the technical approaches considered at that time require some detailed explanation in order to assess their relevance and the effectiveness of the tracing system.

This session is sought to be very interactive, discussing the different points of view and understanding of three main issues: how the contagion spreads and how the identification of groups at risk may be done, the information needed by healthcare staff to undertake the notification process, and the possibilities provided by the technology using a smartphone.

Before the second session the students read a longer paper. This article introduces some ethical issues and, in particular, the consideration of rights: public and individual health and safety, and privacy. Also, it includes some references to documents published during spring 2020 about the ethical issues of tracing systems [3], [4], [5], [6]. Again, students are asked to take the questionnaire before the discussion in class. The comparison of the answers allows to assess how the first session helped the students to understand the technical requirements and how introducing new aspects modify their previous assessment.

2.1 The questionnaire

The first part of the questionnaire aims to make an assessment about how a better understanding of the problem and of the techniques changes the answers of the students and their initial assessment. The poll is anonymous, so individual changes of opinion cannot be analysed.

A set of questions in the questionnaire deals about the understanding of the effectiveness of different technologies used for the identification of the close contacts of a new diagnosed patient. Another set of questions introduces the issue of privacy and asks for a comparative assessment of the alternatives considered.

The goal of the questionnaire is to compare the opinions of the students about the effectiveness and privacy issues of the proposed tracing approaches before discussing about the ethical challenges and after doing so. The expected result is that when ethical issues are included in the discussion some design options are discarded or avoided while others may require some changes in their design.

2.2 The main aspects to be addressed during the discussion sessions

A list of the different aspects analysed during the sessions follows.

Understanding the effectiveness of testing, not only to detect a contagion but as a requirement for all people identified to be at risk because of being a close contact.

The identification process of the group at risk and its conditions: to be close enough (about 1 or 2 meters) during a minimum period of time (about 10-15 minutes) during the past two weeks.

How automatic identification helps to cut the spread of the contagion and the effect of false positives and false negatives. The accuracy of the technology used for the identification process is a key factor in the overall usefulness and performance.

The importance of the notification process and how an automatic notification can be made preserving the privacy of the patient and of the people detected as close contact. A successful notification requires not only the collaboration of the patient but of the notified people too, as they should go voluntarily to take a test as soon as possible.

Next comes the analysis of the effectiveness of different technical approaches: mobile operators may be required to provide the locations of user's phones (this aggregated information allows to follow the spread of the contagion but cannot identify close contacts); the collection of venue QR codes, the collection of personal

QR codes (these may not work well enough as many people may be in the same place but not close to each other); the use of GPS geo-location to track people (this may be seen as a massive surveillance system and it may not work properly indoors); the use of Bluetooth for detecting nearby devices during a continuous period of time and estimating their proximity (to do this an improved version of the drivers is needed and it may be easily distributed in an update of the smartphone's operating system).

In a broad sense there are two approaches for developing a tracing system. The centralised approach collects routinely all the information provided by the applications (basically, location, date and time, and user's or device identification) in a central server. The information is available to the healthcare staff at any time.

On the other hand, the decentralised approach keeps all the information stored in the mobile device. This information will be used to help tracing possible groups of people at risk only if the owner of the device is diagnosed as infected. Respect for privacy depends on how the information provided by the tracing application is managed and used.

The idea of using non-personal identification is introduced and the effectiveness of this "ideal" approach should be assessed. Though no personal identification is used the effectiveness of the identification and notification processes may be the same as implementations using personal identification which may lead to privacy issues. The privacy-preserving tracing concept is introduced.

The last set of questions in the questionnaire asks for an assessment of the privacy of the technical alternatives considered before.

At this point, while analysing the answers of the questionnaire it is the time to introduce other technical and non-technical aspects, such as the accuracy measuring the distances using Bluetooth, the relevance of false negatives, some characteristics of decentralized and centralized systems, the necessary level of social acceptance (that is, the required percentage of citizens using the tracing application for the system to be useful) and some other issues related with privacy rights.

It is expected to be the turning point of the discussion that requires a back step and reconsider the previous alternatives to make a proper assessment.

3 RESULTS

The results of this experience are presented following the discussion of the answers of the questionnaire. This section is organized in three subsections: effectiveness of the methods, identification of privacy issues of the methods under study, and an assessment of the privacy issues of the methods and systems proposed.

3.1 Effectiveness of the technology used for tracing

Table 1 presents a comparison of the results of the first and second questionnaires (labelled as “a” and “b”) related to the effectiveness of the eight different technologies proposed. The answers grade from “not useful” (1), “somewhat useful” (2), “useful” (3), to “very useful” (4).

Due to space limitation, a detailed description of each of the methods (identification and notification processes) are not included.

Table 1. Effectiveness of the method as a percentage of the answers

Method	Answers	Questionnaire 1 (a)	Questionnaire 2 (b)
1- Collect phone id from Base Station	2	50%	50%
	3	25%	7%
2- Collect personal QR at venues	1+2	58%	49%
	3	25%	50%
3- Collect QR of the venues in the phone	1+2	67%	43%
	3	16.5%	43%
4- GPS coordinates sent to a server	1+2	68%	50%
	3+4	32%	50%
5- Store GPS coordinates in the phone	1+2	67%	43%
	3+4	33%	57%
6- Collect BT data in a server	3	41.7%	21.4%
	4	8.3%	57%
7- Store BT data in the phone	3+4	33%	57.2%
8- Store BT anonymous data in phone	3+4	58%	50%
	4	17.7%	35.7%

As expected, a better understanding of the method is reflected in the answers of questionnaire 2 (b). For instance, collecting phone numbers in the coverage area of a mobile base station is not really useful (7%). The effectiveness of QR codes depends on the continuous effort of the citizens to scan the codes. That is why the effectiveness of the method cannot be really assessed. On the other hand, it is difficult to explain why storing GPS coordinates in the phone is considered more efficient than sending them to a server (57% vs. 50%). Finally, using anonymous Bluetooth identifiers is perceived as less efficient than using the real Bluetooth identifier (50% vs. 57.2%). This suggests that the complete mechanism was not well understood even after reading the second article.

The discussion during the second session confirms this point. A detailed explanation about how using random identifiers for the devices may allow the identification and notification of close contacts took a significant amount of time.

3.2 Identification of privacy issues

The questionnaire includes several situations and asks for an assessment about privacy respect in each case. The answers are graded as: “no issues”, “some issues”, and “not acceptable”.

There are some surprising results. For instance, asked about the privacy of collecting the name, date, location and the name of nearby people (potential close contacts) is seen as acceptable by 25% of the students before the first session and it drops to 14% only after the session. Clearly, privacy has different perceptions in different cultures. It is seen as unacceptable by 50% of them in questionnaire 1 (a) and raise slightly to 57% in questionnaire 2 (b).

Other results are as expected. For instance, making public the list of tracks of infected people (including location, date and time, but not the name) is considered to be unacceptable (91.7% and 100%, respectively).

3.3 Assessment of the privacy issues of the methods proposed

Figure 1 shows the assessment about the privacy issues raised by each of the eight methods proposed. The assessment about the privacy has four options: i) no privacy issues, ii) health rights prevail over privacy, iii) a balance between health rights and privacy rights is required, and iv) there are serious privacy issues and the method must be avoided. The method is numbered from 1 to 8 (as in Table 1). Answers in questionnaire 1 are labelled as “a” and the ones in questionnaire 2 as “b”. That is, column 8b corresponds to the results of questionnaire 2 about the method “store Bluetooth anonymous data in the phone”.

Figure 1. Assessment of the privacy issues

Centralised systems (columns 4 and 6) show a significant level of rejection (serious privacy issues). This corresponds to the social rejection of anything that may be used as a mass surveillance system.

Column 8b shows that the use of anonymous Bluetooth identifiers was not really understood after reading the papers. At the end of the second session the majority of the students agreed that some privacy aspects should be balanced but basically privacy is properly preserved.

4 SUMMARY

The discussion sessions highlight the difficulty of understanding the details of the problem and its real requirements. Also, the description of the characteristics of the different technologies requires to go into some detail about the possible implementation of the tracing system.

In particular, the privacy preserving approach using random Bluetooth identifiers is not intuitive and requires some effort to understand that it can provide the same information that the approach using personal identifiers while preserving personal privacy from the very beginning. A useful explanation may be found in [8] and [9].

The consideration of the social impact is related with the voluntary collaboration of the citizens, first installing the tracing application and afterwards accepting to provide their information to identify close contacts, and second, the collaboration of close contacts for taking a test. This point raises the key issue of trust. Citizens must trust healthcare authorities, politicians, and developers of the system. Without trust the acceptance ratio is too low for the system to be useful as a tracing tool. Trust includes also that the data collected will be used only for the declared purpose and by authorized staff only.

During the discussion, a detailed comment of the statement published by ACM [5] helps to understand the concrete requirements derived from the personal privacy right in order to design and deploy a privacy-preserving tracing system.

Including the assessment of the privacy issues in the different approaches helps to avoid some of them or, at least, some of the possible implementations. Imposing a high requirement for privacy lead to groups of engineers to find privacy-preserving methods that were implemented in the most common support for tracing systems developed jointly by Apple and Google for their mobile operating systems [9].

This is a nice example of “ethics by design”. Ethical considerations were put at the starting point of the design and that allowed to find an innovative way to implement the system.

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